

The concept of enterprise environmental factors applies to an input or output system designed to identify aspects that are beyond the project team's control but have a substantial impact on how the project is managed, programme, or portfolio's outcome. This influence can be beneficial or detrimental. The phrase is not often used, but the notion is critical, as most, if not all, projects are influenced by the environment in which they are handled. If you find it difficult to access external resources and your project team is unable to meet the required capabilities, then this could be an indication of an enterprise environment issue.

Despite their title, they are not limited to circumstances that the business defines; they can also allude to elements that the business must deal with, including industry laws. Environmental influences in the workplace might include, and are not limited to:

- A. The organization's structure and culture
- B. Industry norms or government norms
- C. Existing human resources
- D. Infrastructural components
- E. Communications channels
- F. Political climate
- G. Market circumstance
- H. Project management system

Environmental influences in the workplace can be measured in a variety of methods, but adequate documentation is crucial. These are often inputs but they are clearly an outcome of the project's initial stages. The project team may also have access to human resources. These resources can impact the company's environment. Managers and the team need to be aware of these factors, even if they're not listed in the PMBOK as intake to a process category.

Although projects are transient in nature, they are rarely carried out in isolation. Enterprise Environmental Factors (EEF) & Organizational Process Assets affect them while they work in a regulated environment (OPA).

The project management information system, which is included [visit this link](#) in the environmental factors, gives users access to tools like service software, an approval system, a configuration control system, an information collection & distribution system, and interfaces to certain other online automated systems. This system can include automated data collection & reports on key performance indicators.

PMIS Software endorses Integration Management, Project Scope Management and Time Management. PMIS Software can also be hosted in the cloud or on-premises.

The PMIS is a collection of tools and processes that allow managers to deliver information. managers employ procedures and tools to gather, synthesize, and disseminate data via electronic & manual means. Upper & lower management use PMIS to communicate with one another.

PMIS assists in planning, execution, as well as completion of management goals. PMIS is used by project managers to budget and estimate costs during the planning process. The PMIS is also used to determine the scope baseline and create a specified schedule. The PMIS is a database that gathers all information necessary to achieve project management goals. The PMIS is being used to evaluate the baseline of the current situation.

1. Scheduling and planning

A PMIS could plan and compute the project's critical path and schedule, whether it was done using built-in scheduling tools or an interface to scheduling tools like Microsoft Project and Oracle Primavera P6. A PMIS could set the scope baseline, construct or import the project's schedule.

2. Budgeting and Forecasting

A good PMIS will allow you to associate costs with specific tasks or components in order to make more accurate budget forecasts. A PMIS must contain project cost estimation, forecasting, cost data and schedule information. This will allow you to assess project performance and progress. All of this information is available in one location, so expenses can be tracked throughout planning, estimation, and execution.

3. Procurement and Resource Management

Because resources and procured products account for a substantial amount of a project's cost and preliminary budget, a PMIS must have the capabilities to manage the entire procurement process.

4. Project Management & Cost Control

Project managers can control project cost & performance with a good PMIS. They can update their plans and compare actual results to anticipated data changes. It also gives them what-if scenarios. All this while managing project modifications. Additional project values, such as planned value and real costs, can be calculated to show the project's current status & performance from a budget or schedule standpoint.

5. Progress Reporting

Created project progress reporting saves project managers time while providing them with the tools they need to build and send reports suited to diverse audiences. A PMIS will be able to generate and share reports based on data that has been collected and processed.

6. System and Data Integration

PMIS is required to bring together all project information in order to eliminate data silos. A PMIS must be able to be incorporated with other software or applications. This system integration enables multi-project assessment & the bridging of gaps across systems and applications required to get all information in a single place.